

MIMS 4.01 - Morality as a Simulation of Holiness

Where MIMS 4.0 is the “New Religion” as of yet unborn; See also
MIMS 2.8 - War

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ABSTRACT

The Exact causes and conditions of morality are quite multi-faceted. Herein the author discusses potentially unique topics (from an EPEMC perspective) as it relates to morality’s mimsical benefits, as well as the abstractification of Holiness, which could affect our use of morality as either a MIMS or anti-MIMS (weaponized morality). Does the “divine right to rule” touch upon this subject? Suggested for further study: data, research, and especially a direct analysis of the philosophical and factual contrast of morality and ethics.

Key Words: morality - ethics - religion - holiness - war - war on terror - MIMS

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Membranous Interface of Material and Spiritual

MIMS 4.0 Recalling the New Religion	3
Holiness - A War Perspective	4
Holy War	5
MIMS 4.01 - Morality As a Simulation	8
The Terror of the War on Terror	9
Morality Wars	11
Weaponized Misery	13
Conclusions?	14
References	15

MIMS 4.0 Recalling the New Religion

In a pre-MIMS work titled, “Parameterization of New Religion utilizing EPEMC and Western Humanistic Egalitarianism as a guide,”¹ the author talked about engineering a “New Religion” which will actually connect mankind from the present modern day way of living to past systems, using Western egalitarian humanism for its ethics (WEHE). We do not therefore need to cover the ethics portion of the New Religion here. However, we should recall that in “Conquering the Solar System,”² the author outlined in Part 3 a series of known MIMS which were critical to human success in not only surviving the cataclysms but thriving. Religion, as detailed in “On the Origins of Religions”³ was one such designed MIMS (taking thousands of years to evolve) which gave mankind a huge edge over other simian competitors and the ability to take over the planet and reshape it.

The results are undeniable. Nearly 8 billion people, with relative peace attained through a complicated and interconnected web of Finance (MIMS 2.5)⁴ and Government (MIMS 2.7)⁵ related connections, such as economics, law, contracts (as of yet not discussed anywhere in MIMS literature and with ancient Mesopotamian connections!), etc.

In religion you need not only ethics, and governance, you need Morality. But why? In this short paper the author wants to discuss Morality as a vital MIMS which strains credulity sometimes, and leads to many issues (because of the “slipperiness of the Law of Relativity”) and yet remains unrivaled in production by anti-Moralist systems, many of which are undeniably anti-MIMS themselves (such as Luciferianism/Satanism, or “black magick,” or crime for that matter).

Before closing this Introduction let the author make clear his *libertine* stance: you can believe anything you like, and within the limits of your freedom (Clear and Present Danger doctrine⁶), he believes you should be *mostly* able to do what you want. However, he isn’t here to impose a specific set of morals upon you. But let it be made clear the author does not assert that the “rainbow of gray” of morality is an absolute construct of the Divine - of the “Big G”⁷ - and that just as you must “be careful what you wish for” you must also be careful what you believe in. There are absolute right and wrong, Good and Evil, as can be demonstrated with simple

1

https://www.academia.edu/38206009/Parameterization_of_New_Religion_utilizing_EPEMC_and_Western_Humanistic_Egalitarianism_as_a_guide

2 https://www.academia.edu/62757621/Conquering_the_Solar_System

3 https://www.academia.edu/36753645/On_the_Origins_of_Religions

4

https://www.academia.edu/50902057/MIMS_2_5_1_Financial_Velocity_Addendum_A_Follow_up_on_Interesting_Developments_in_the_N_power

5

https://www.academia.edu/51641990/MIMS_2_7_8_War_and_Government_The_Rise_and_Fall_of_US_Military_Dominance_from_an_Art_of_War_perspective_and_MIMS_Analysis_as_well_as_a_short_discussion_of_the_history_of_failures_of_government_programs_from_antiquity_through_the_Great_Enlightenment

6 https://www.law.cornell.edu/wex/clear_and_present_danger.

7

https://www.academia.edu/53271235/Explication_of_the_Versatility_of_the_Big_G_diagram_in_MIMS_1_0

polar maths and boolean logic. That being said, let us openly and freely discuss morality as a MIMS. Right after we discuss what it is simulating.

Holiness - A War Perspective

As the reader is aware, in EPEMC we have a tacit and continual theme of discussing the idea that religion simulates the truly divine, and that the planetary motions, arc events, cataclysms, etc. were *interpreted* as being holy wars and holy edicts (such as the Tablets of Destiny⁸, or the Exodus event⁹, or the war in the Gita¹⁰), but the knowledgeable - such as Moshe - understood them to be events of greater meaning. There is an implication in the Chinese plasmaglyphics that the One Above is above the “Great Man” and that makes it “Heaven.”¹¹ Also that this Great Man (Shang Di)¹² was capable to hold the gas giants under His arms was shown in other analyses to be categorically related to the Weapons of the God/Lord and therefore that the Father-Son → Father-Son motif and the Father+Mother → Two Brothers → Husband & Wife → Warring Titans → War of the demigods was nothing more than a demonstrable breakdown of the dwarf star Ra/Shamash/EI¹³ and the disintegration of the previous solar system arrangement and formation of present day, unexplainable by accretion, arrangement.¹⁴

However, let us suppose for a moment that as this is a MIMS paper and we somewhat pre-suppose the spiritual phenomenon to be “real”¹⁵, that there is some grander **absolute** (with all the meaning that is implied therein and constrained by the Law of Conservation to be held firm) reality wherein a right and wrong “fabric” is the “measuring stick” or “standards”¹⁶ whereby the Law of Causation pulls its calculating data from in order to perform the linear and nonlinear operations we are familiar with in:

- ❖ Karma
- ❖ Newtonian Physics
- ❖ Chemistry
- ❖ Ten Commandments
- ❖ Justice
- ❖ Causality
- ❖ Etc.

⁸ 2.7 Ibid. pp. 21, 26

⁹ Ala “Worlds in Collision,” I. Velikovsky, 1950

<https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/eu-general/giants-of-eu-history/velikovsky>

¹⁰ http://www.bhagavatgita.ru/files/Bhagavad-gita_As_It_Is.pdf

¹¹ https://www.academia.edu/38590072/Shang_Di_Heaven_and_Dao

¹² https://www.academia.edu/38744706/Uchell_the_High_Lord_and_Shang_Di

¹³

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/354010454_Addendum_2_Megafauna_Extinction_Events_Update_to_the_Thunderbolt_Extinction_Model_the_Surprising_truth_of_the_Younger_Dryas_Event_that_Changes_Everything

¹⁴ <https://www.space.com/2206-death-spiral-theorists-cant-solar-systems.html>

¹⁵ Whether ‘digitized’ or ‘sampled’ into psychological and neurochemistry, or approached from the perspective of occult mysticism.

¹⁶ Proverbs 20:23

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We are speaking, at the root, of the operations of stimulus → response. To date, no matter the verbiage of quantum mechanicians and discussion of problems with qubits¹⁷, no one has been able to supplant it.¹⁸ Therefore, we consider this as our “mathematical” solid base and foundation. We are on a real, firm bedrock of reality here. Causation is distinct and is the “king” of Laws. From it, all authority flows as from Heaven to Earth itself.

Therefore, when we look in the past texts, the Bible, Gita, Upanishads, etc. we see also a continual theme of “Holiness” which is not a MIMS but concrete and real. It is not human made, is the point. Several cultures have made clear that there is a distinct, but perhaps related to “the Force” (*F* power) and tangible ‘force’ at play in our lives which is derived from a Source, most cultures of course name as “Lord” or God directly. This has been covered extensively in the MIMS 1.0x “Big G”¹⁹ series and need not be berated here.

The point is that Holiness is not just a sanctity of behavior, belief, outlook etc. but a viable and real frequency upon which most all treads. It is probably related, and this will be explored in another paper, to Truth.²⁰ Needless to say that is not our specific interest here, as much as the facets of Holy War.

Holy War

War as an anti-MIMS has been covered in the aforementioned MIMS 2.7 & 2.8 paper, and suffice it to say, humanity’s use of war is mostly unjustifiable and simply destructive, stemming from the “worst MIMS ever created”: Government. Nevertheless, governments exist and are a definite and concrete ‘force’ in every single human life on this planet, even those unaware of it at all.²¹ For starters, the “divine right to rule” as a destructive doctrine is not new and quite ancient. It affects our discussions of Sumo²², King Arthur²³, and nuclear weaponry²⁴, for example, amongst myriad topics in EPEMC. But what is curious is not that governments have made extensive, and detestable use of war, but that so few have taken the time to understand what makes a Holy War (in the Heavens) in fact Holy²⁵ (from either the Divine’s perspective, or ours).

Genesis 2:3

Then God blessed the seventh day and made it holy, because on it he rested from all the work of creating that he had done.

¹⁷ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1905.13641>

¹⁸ <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevA.103.042412>

¹⁹ https://www.academia.edu/53713967/MIMS_1_12_Self_Consistency_of_the_Big_G_Diagram

²⁰ <https://bit.ly/3lsecCl>

²¹ Such as Brazilian tribes

²² https://www.academia.edu/38268897/Sumo_Ancient_Ritual_to_the_Thunder_God

²³

https://www.academia.edu/38993303/Caer_Melyn_Camelot_Cosmic_Hillfort_of_the_King_The_Yellow_Hill_fort_as_a_Cosmic_Hill_or_mountain_motif_and_symbol_of_a_Kings_authority

²⁴

https://www.academia.edu/36753646/Investments_in_Ragnarok_Comparisons_and_Conclusions_from_the_study_of_Media_Business_and_Government_investments_in_End_of_the_World_myth_story_and_comparison and 2.7 Ibid. pp. 20-25

²⁵ <https://www.whatchristianswanttoknow.com/what-is-the-biblical-definition-of-holy/>

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Exodus 3:5

“Do not come any closer,” God said. “Take off your sandals, for the place where you are standing is holy ground.”

Exodus 19:23

Moses said to the Lord, “The people cannot come up Mount Sinai, because you yourself warned us, ‘Put limits around the mountain and set it apart as holy.’”

Exodus 20:8

“Remember the Sabbath day by keeping it holy.

Exodus 20:11

For in six days the Lord made the heavens and the earth, the sea, and all that is in them, but he rested on the seventh day. Therefore the Lord blessed the Sabbath day and made it holy.

Exodus 26:34

Put the atonement cover on the ark of the covenant law in the Most Holy Place.

Exodus 28:29

“Whenever Aaron enters the Holy Place, he will bear the names of the sons of Israel over his heart on the breastpiece of decision as a continuing memorial before the Lord.

Exodus 28:35

Aaron must wear it when he ministers. The sound of the bells will be heard when he enters the Holy Place before the Lord and when he comes out, so that he will not die.

Exodus 28:36

“Make a plate of pure gold and engrave on it as on a seal: holy to the Lord.

Exodus 28:43

Aaron and his sons must wear them whenever they enter the tent of meeting or approach the altar to minister in the Holy Place, so that they will not incur guilt and die.

“This is to be a lasting ordinance for Aaron and his descendants.

Exodus 29:37

For seven days make atonement for the altar and consecrate it. Then the altar will be most holy, and whatever touches it will be holy.

Exodus 30:10

Once a year Aaron shall make atonement on its horns. This annual atonement must be made with the blood of the atoning sin offering for the generations to come. It is most holy to the Lord.”

Exodus 30:29

You shall consecrate them so they will be most holy, and whatever touches them will be holy.

Exodus 31:14

“Observe the Sabbath, because it is holy to you. Anyone who desecrates it is to be put to death; those who do any work on that day must be cut off from their people.

Exodus 31:15

For six days work is to be done, but the seventh day is a day of sabbath rest, holy to the Lord. Whoever does any work on the Sabbath day is to be put to death.”

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The author would posit that we have no data, nay not even a basic understanding of whether or not stars and planets have a form of consciousness²⁶ as complexity theory would suggest. If they do, is this (or rather their fields' interactions with our minds, or with Earth and then from Her mind²⁷ to ours²⁸) the origin of Holiness?²⁹ Or is there a Grand Design at play, sort of a "God or is a child playing with marbles" hypothesis that has been posited by others elsewhere? If God is a child playing with marbles, then the Holiness becomes nihilistic happenstance, and mankind can and perhaps *should* despair. But religion is authored by adult men, and adult men make adult games of war and power.

Human power is really a bit of a joke³⁰, unless we speak about nuclear holocaust or genocides, there's nothing funny about those. But men do war to themselves, and at great cost. The causes and conditions of "hyper-masculinity" have been covered elsewhere, and we need not go down that route, either. Suffice it to say, what we are interested in is the real cause of the cataclysms: Holy Judgment, or mere coincidence of the spheres' motions inducing electrical arc and electrokinetic quaking on Earth because the crust is a mere thin, hard membrane between the Spheres of Heaven and the Spheres of Earth?³¹

The author has no final solution at this time for that query.

As to the idea that God is a child of innocence, exploring Himself via new ideas, and making experiments, or allowing aliens (or angels) to simulate their experience through painful avatar-like living within us pitiable apes that have been domesticated for slavery³² and war... well that's almost more horrifying than the occasional Scholz's Star³³ or Nemesis/Black God³⁴ running rampant through the solar system, inducing catastrophe! It appears that the Egyptians saw the approach of Apollo as a form of Satan/Set, coming to rip apart his "brother" (Ra/Osiris), and later on this theme repeated in the arc exchanges of the now severed red dwarf in Jupiter and proto-Saturn. The arc exchanges, then left Osiris severed and splayed throughout the solar system, the "intestines" of the god hung in the "tree" of plasma energy³⁵. Was then Jupiter now Horus, set to avenge his father by battling the Sun/Sol/Set? We may never know so long as

²⁶ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/researchers/clarage>

²⁷

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/282970524_The_Gaia_Hypothesis_Science_on_a_Pagan_Planet

²⁸

<https://courses.seas.harvard.edu/climate/eli/Courses/EPS281r/Sources/Gaia/Gaia-hypothesis-wikipedia.pdf>

²⁹ <http://csmgeo.csm.jmu.edu/geollab/fichter/geobio350/gaiatest.PDF>

³⁰ The strongest punch ever measured as a whopping 1750 PSI or so. This is pretty laughable compared to the mantis shrimp: 510,000 PSI in human equivalence (1500 N)

<https://www.quora.com/If-there-was-a-human-sized-mantis-shrimp-would-it-beat-Floyd-Mayweather>

³¹

https://www.academia.edu/36753643/Our_Plasma_Electromagnetic_Sky_Application_of_Hollow_Expanding_Growing_Electromagnetic_Earth_Hypothesis_with_particular_respect_to_the_Earths_Atmosphere_starting_from_the_Lithosphere_and_ascending_Altitude

³² Ala "The 12th Planet," Z. Sitchin

³³ <https://www.rochester.edu/newscenter/scholz-star/>

³⁴ If indeed Nemesis is not Typhon but is potentially a black body "Planet 9" as the Mayans seem to be suggesting.

³⁵ The author proposes the tree is merely the LaGrangian arrangement, see Part 2 of Addendum 2. Pp. 43-44

present day Egyptology translates everything according to certain Victorian dictates³⁶. But perhaps the Tepe culture will give us the raw data anyhow, and may prove to be our hope and “salvation.” Or the Columbian Rock Art.³⁷

Regardless, our main interest in the rest of the paper is not in the true facet of the Force and Lord (*L* power) as applied to consciousness and in the service of understanding Holiness as a frequency³⁸. Our main concern is how humanity responds to this proposed frequency (and the Changes³⁹) *if they are real and concrete*. The safest assumption to make is that they are, and then react to this “dictates” with a sort of “dharma”⁴⁰ like consciousness. But in so doing, might we be living a form of simulation (regardless of any video game tropes, mind you) that keeps us constrained in ways unnecessary, and which may, in fact, enable the very evils we wish to postpone or destroy? The author himself is curious, and therefore, let us enter within MIMS 4.01 and discuss it further.⁴¹

MIMS 4.01 - Morality As a Simulation⁴²

When we simulate Holiness, we create cultural mores and norms (which evolve and are purposefully and coincidentally altered) that we call ‘morality.’ In point of fact modern morals are quite a bit different than in the remote past, and this is, for the most part, a good thing. It falls down when moral relativism rejects the obviousness of absolute Truth and therefore good and bad, right and wrong (ethics) and Good and Evil for a form of *laissez faire* / “anything goes” / “YOLO”⁴³ - Bacchian - way of life. These ways of life invariably show fault and failure. People know, too, they are wrong as they try to shield children from these facets of adult life and lasciviousness, instinctively. When two consenting adulterers are caught cheating they both cover up with sheets and go white as the sheets with embarrassment and shame. These natural instincts were likened by Mencius (Mengzi) to be signs of the innate goodness of mankind inside himself/herself.⁴⁴ But the Judeo-Christians saw the fact of the sinful life as signs of the internalized Sin of mankind from the Fall in the Garden of Eden. The fact that the EDIN was a cosmic place in the sky is irrelevant to the discussion of morality, and we do not need to try to

³⁶ Slaves, death cults, incest, etc

³⁷

https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1QnRXGf1kju3C_CZX06njKK-tnrbGGjq5kOGkRAI-zSM/edit?usp=sharing

³⁸ Law of Vibration, implying *P* power.

³⁹ Law of Evolution/Flux as applied to space-flux / time.

⁴⁰ <https://www.britannica.com/topic/dharma-religious-concept>

⁴¹ Morality seems so central to Religion, that it seems like it deserves a 4.1 designation, but actually it is intrinsic to religion so it must be beneath Religion itself. This would retcon “On the Origins of Religion” to MIMS 4.0!!

⁴² Remember: here we do not mean as a computer simulation but as an attempt at.

⁴³ You only live once; a ridiculous supposition

⁴⁴ “In advising a disciple debating a Mohist, from a rival school to early Confucianism that critiqued Confucians’ insistence on elaborate rituals and other wasteful uses of material resources, Mengzi invokes the sense of respect by telling a story about a society in which people did not bury their parents, abandoning them in open ditches. Later, when they passed the bodies of their deceased parents and saw “foxes were eating them, bugs were sucking on them. Sweat broke out on the survivors’ foreheads. They turned away and did not look” (3A5). Here their sprouts react to their failure to respect their parents.”

<https://1000wordphilosophy.com/2018/04/10/mengzis-moral-psychology-part-1-the-four-moral-sprouts/>

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connect the two except to point out the following intriguing fact about the Greek gods: they were constantly involved in lasciviousness, vanity, affairs, incest⁴⁵, and war even over petty jealousies. The fact that these are inherited Babylonian and Egyptian descriptions of cosmic events that were then anthropomorphized is not as interesting as how people did this. They made the gods almost *amoral*.

Why?

Mankind, and let us focus on the West where our WEHE evolved and now dominates the globe even with defacto UN sanctions, has rejected the gods' amoral stance in favor of:

- Rule of Law; again probably related to the Force and Divine Right to Rule (via Aquinas, et al.) but also possibly to this so called 'moral force' (De in Chinese)
- Morality

But why morality? In fact as a MIMS it is really quite arbitrary and hit or miss. In any church, and indeed often from the top, you will find an incredible amount of corruption and hypocrisy. Humans love attacking each others' morals (or immorality) almost as much as they love the act of sinning and being immoral itself. Purity is desired, mostly so it can be muddied. People enjoy sullyng the good moods of others. "Misery loves company" as the saying goes. Morally speaking, you will be lucky if you meet a moral person in your life, and then you are probably looking at a sexual deviant. We won't need to go into lengthy proofs of the Taijitu (yin/yang diagram) to show that in all the white there is always black, and vice versa. Many stories are written of the virtuousness of the most heinous criminals trying to "do the right thing" (from vigilantes to hitmen to bank robbers⁴⁶). But few stories ever portray the man or woman that has "Fallen Down" as a hero. We love heroes, and we love to see them fail/fall. Is that a Mars motif? Probably. But not right now!

Right now we want to dive into this idea that morality (and probably "justice itself") is in fact a simulation of Holiness. Let us return to the terrible failure that is the "War on Terror".

The Terror of the War on Terror

9/11 was horrific, made all the more horrific by the facts of the complex nature of its meaning, exegesis, and outcomes. If USA ® was still a righteous government, instead of the anti-MIMS it has become (as it slowly morphs into the neo-feudal and fascist dictatorship in less than 20 years since 9/11), the response would have been the following:

1. Pray as a world and as a nation.
2. Find Osama Bin Laden et al.
3. Locate all the accounts and names/GPS of those associated

⁴⁵ <https://therisingsouls.wordpress.com/2012/10/06/brahmas-incest-with-his-daughter-sarasvati/>

While the author doesn't condone the anti-Hindu slant of the article, it makes solid points about morality issues as relates to religion, in this case in India. It is also a bit amusing to watch the author make the serious claim that the god was impregnating lotuses, when obviously the incest and behavior talked about here is anthropomorphizing of cosmic motions in the sky. For example when Shiva "cuts the head off Brahma" for his "profligate behavior" actually this is talking about a specific cosmic event. Identifying that event will be the job of EPEMC post 2023 after the GR treatment and more electrogeology is done. Tackling the Upanishads and Rig Veda in 2022-2023 would bite off more than this author can chew!

⁴⁶ Even nearly 100 years later the "John Dillinger" movie portrayed him as a folk hero, which ... actually he was. He was also a murderer.

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Membranous Interface of Material and Spiritual

4. Locate all the co-conspirators, no matter their wealth or status
5. Eliminate all in a simultaneous strike.
6. Pray for the world to heal.
7. Heal the wounded and families.
8. Care for the EMS exposed to asbestos

But that is *not* what happened⁴⁷. Obviously the author is in full support of the brave soldiers, especially the “Horse Soldiers” who were acting in a righteous war against Al Qaeda and their allies in the Taliban. The author also supported with actual efforts the removal of Saddam Hussein. However, that’s about the end of righteous actions taken by the “coalition of the willing.” The rest of it was based on lies, deception, military contracts for the Military Industrial Complex, expansion of the USA ® into innocent - and especially American/patriot - lives etc. These are historical facts that need not be revisited to make the point, especially after the botched Afghanistan pullout and all of the moral and ethical “existential crisis.”

The point is that whatever the causes and conditions were for 9/11, the War on Terror turned more into a Terror War than anything, and helped us define the anti-MIMS. It didn’t make anyone safer, much less children or Americans. It made the world a much scarier place and closer to World War III. We are still feeling the ramifications of the evil behaviors of MIC greed now, only the world’s economics are weaker, and there is both a host of nonlinear dynamical diseases and a plannedemic with recurrent false flag epidemics giving power to evil tyrants throughout the West. The spread of Useful Idiocy remains prevalent, and teachers⁴⁸ and professors are getting fired for standing up to immoral racism!⁴⁹ All of these things are Hell Unleashed by the poor and unrighteous decisions (of a “Christian” President no less⁵⁰) post 9/11. Why do we put up with it? We put up with it because the world is now so much more confused that many people do not know right from wrong anymore (or even male from female), and this hits the author in a personal way! It has affected many lives, especially since 2017.

Nevertheless our interest here is not a deep dive into the New Cold War, as has already been done by the author⁵¹, it is in the concept of a Holy War. Let us then define the Holy War or rather not jihad but *War based on Holiness* as:

- ★ The exact polar opposite, or dually opposed, vision of the War on Terror, with the exception that the origin can still be a surprise/shock which most believe to be wholly an issue of terrorism⁵².
 - What a terrible definition... it is as if there is no definition in terms of visual scope!

⁴⁷ In the words of one politician of the party of systemic racism, “Never let a good crisis go to waste.”

⁴⁸

<https://www.foxnews.com/politics/indiana-teacher-exposed-crt-teaching-leave-email-locked-banned-school-buildings>

⁴⁹ <https://www.foxnews.com/us/ucla-professor-lawsuit-grades-leniently-suspension>

⁵⁰ Can President Bush serve two masters in the Skull n Bones society, and Jesus? The author is doubtful.

⁵¹ https://www.academia.edu/51022722/Winning_the_New_Cold_War_World_War_3

⁵² The facts of the conspiracy of 9/11 remain unavailable (despite being on the web) to most people.

Morality Wars

Most people are 'good', rather most people are wheat and not tares⁵³. Well, that depends on your outlook. If you're raised to think that man is irredeemable, then most people would not be good enough to enter Heaven after death. If your outlook is that most people *try to do the right thing*, which is factual, even if it creates a form of Hell⁵⁴ then you'll tend to think "every little thing is gonna be alright."⁵⁵ Actually when mankind lives by this, many rapes and child abuses get swept under the rug. But when people catch the thief, rapist, arson, or pedophile in the act, the reaction is usually swift and vengeful. In point of fact people are vengeful and there are a good number of cultures that still honor revenge killings, especially for the death of a family member unjustly.

But let's say that most people *must* be good, or else then murder etc. would be far more prevalent than the reverse. In which case, people try to assimilate and simulate Holiness in their interactions. When they are not behaving selfishly or with vice, people are, even down to a man as evil as Pol Pot or Stalin, acting for occasional morality. In fact many make a show of it! Why?

Simulation is like imitation, and imitation is the sincerest form of flattery. People want Heaven to shine on them benevolently. The irony is that the Chinese noted that Heaven makes it rain for the good and evil alike, and everyone - even Hitler - had a mother. Earth provides food for the just and unjust alike, and does not (contrary to our hopes) favor the good over the evil. In fact, frequently evil things do happen to perfectly good people. The horror stories of these events of Causation are enough to make a pure preacher turn white as a ghost. It's terrifying to know that in fact morality does not do this trick: make only bad things happen to 'bad people'.

War based on Holiness is, however in this author's opinion, an example of the attempt of mankind to attune to a greater/higher frequency than our "base nature" and then act upon that. It means to "turn the other cheek" no matter how hard, except when you cannot (like Pearl Harbor). It means to await the conditions of Heaven and/or God to evolve or revolve⁵⁶ the situation into more favorable circumstances. Unfortunately it also means "turning a blind eye" to many evils in our day(s)!

So here is the million dollar question: if morality is the plasma and holiness the anode around which it hovers or attempts to simulate... what benefit - if any does it provide as a MIMS?

Figure 1 - Plasma around anode ([gif](#))

Because as many positive results come from morality (behavioral and material), it *seems* just as likely to produce conflict and strife and even act as an anti-MIMS. The author is not giving credence to the Black Lives Matter© "relative morality" assertion that crime itself is a racial prejudice, that would be a racist assumption that criminality is a WEHE doctrine! In fact all cultures whether tribal or civilized have had a code of ethics and legal regulations which they

⁵³ Matthew 13:24-30

⁵⁴ The road to Hell is paved with good intentions.

⁵⁵ Ala Bob Marley

⁵⁶ Law of Rotation, again part of *P* power.

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enforced, even with death for minor offenses! But it is interesting to note that the morality of the day is still assumed from a Judeo-Christian standing, rather than in biological or modern terms. For example, returning to adultery, a great many liaisons are actually biological:

- Drive to procreate
- Pheromones
- Strong electricity and magnetism, even unwanted, between those having the affair
- Women's bodies also encourage them to have multiple partners
- Men are designed to procreate as much as possible for an entire lifetime

But we also know that if people mess around with others' spouses that violence is possibly an outcome^{57, 58}. How should one follow the other? Morality can therefore definitely be an anti-MIMS. It appears to be trying to approach a high and mighty, perhaps Just?, and lofty goal: the correct behavior of humanity.

Does it achieve this? The author does not have any idea, and probably a certain study would need to be conducted to get data (*N* power) behind the information. It does appear to be working constructively overall. But it isn't even clear to the author how that would be done, without just focusing upon sex. Sex is more of a biological and neurological issue, and a mimsical one at that, than it is a morality discussion. The morals involved with sex are even less obvious than those of a good or bad diet. At least in a diet you see the results tangibly. Saving STDs, and rape (which is more about power), sex has no obvious signs of moral outflux. "Slick Willy"⁵⁹ remained an incredibly popular President with girls and women of the Democrat party long after the facts of his affairs, abuse of power, lying, coverups, and the reprehensible actions of Hillary Clinton against those women came to light. Everything was spun into the case as mentioned before: a criminal trying to do the right thing, rather than a good man fallen from grace. Given the facts of his having an illegitimate black son by a prostitute in Arkansas, and Hillary covering it up, it is not really too far fetched to say people knew he was not a "good man."⁶⁰ But theoretically the President should be held to a higher standard. One supposes, after President Trump, that this might be a far stretch to believe. If the best hope for America is a man renowned for "grabbing [women] by the pussy"⁶¹ (sic) then there is something rotten at any rate about the USA ®.⁶²

The point the author is making is that morality is so loosely defined, and slippery, and highly dependent on mores and cultural assumptions and variability. Look at China right now. Peng Shuai was a woman clearly raped by a prominent politician⁶³, and the entire government

⁵⁷ <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/22747330/>

⁵⁸

<https://oxford.universitypressscholarship.com/view/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780198207634.001.0001/acprof-9780198207634-chapter-6>

⁵⁹ Bill Clinton

⁶⁰ After all, he did take personal responsibility for the deaths of the children at Waco... and did not resign!

⁶¹ <https://www.nytimes.com/2016/10/08/us/donald-trump-tape-transcript.html>

⁶² Again we are not talking about the original United States of America (circa 1776) but the corporation since 1871. And especially the empire post T. Roosevelt and even more so post WW II

⁶³ <https://www.whatsonweibo.com/the-silent-storm-peng-shuais-weibo-post/>

EPEMC :: Philosophy
Membranous Interface of Material and Spiritual

(and now she herself⁶⁴) tried to cover it up⁶⁵. Is this because morality, being only a simulation, is subject to hidden rules? Or is it more of a pattern of using morality as a weapon because everyone wants to justify their personal wars as righteous vengeance? Think about the concept of the movie “The Avengers.”⁶⁶ Setting aside the morality discussions in the more intellectually deep sequels, the first one is a classic war of the gods (and aliens) black/white trope with Loki (planet Venus) as the clear and clearly defined villain. He has even a chance to redeem himself and instead fulfills both the Venus/Mars and Set/Osiris archetypes by stabbing Thor (planet Mars) in the side! What is interesting is this does *not* stop Thor from using his power over the Force and frying the aliens! And in the end: Loki gets captured. Later the stories convolute and that all kind of alters. But the return to a black and white morality is fascinating to see.

Morality might just be, in the end surmise, the *exhaust* of the Rule of Law (a clearly better MIMS, and with more definite benefit) created by societies’ social orders to justify (a) controlling the population with fear and power games and (b) taking righteous wars to their neighbors to persecute them.

There’s nowhere made more clear this anti-MIMSical analysis than in the “heroic” actions of David in the Bible:

- Kills friend
- Takes his wife
- Murders
- Steals giants’ lands
- Idolizer
- Falls from grace
- Redeemed anyways
- Forever hero for slaying a giant defending his own land

Now if David is quite capable of showing us how slippery the rules of morality are, then what hope do we have in our tunnel vision of our lives to know precisely what to do in every situation, no matter what?

Weaponized Misery

Morality is being weaponized most recently in the destructive #metoo (which totally ignores male rape victims), #BLM (which makes blacks into victims and whites into oppressors⁶⁷), and “cancel culture” which is probably better to be named “cancer culture” because of the way it eats away at the West and destroys lives and livelihoods!

⁶⁴ <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-china-59376438>

⁶⁵

https://www.espn.com/tennis/story/_/id/32906809/peng-shuai-tells-newspaper-china-never-wrote-being-sexually-assaulted-post-said-different

⁶⁶ “If we can’t protect the Earth, you can be damn sure we’ll avenge it!” ~Tony Stark/Ironman
This is a strange thing to say in most contexts, but if you think about it, it exactly defines the erratic self-defensive behavior of humanity as the abused/wronged partner in the relationship with the god-planets.

⁶⁷ <https://docs.google.com/document/u/0/d/1uC6BnnWpJkyQTdJv53izWUmK2wpjicHYNHkM7dgGajg/edit>

EPEMC :: Philosophy
Membranous Interface of Material and Spiritual

All of these are either emergent properties of the sick West or more likely created tools of the social marxists for the weaponization of morality and destruction of the West⁶⁸. The smart money bets on the latter. Either way, the anti-MIMS behavior of morality makes the author think that, in some ways, morality is a terrible MIMS and quite unfit as a simulation of Holiness.

The author would tend to think therefore, that rather than moralizing, or letting others demoralize one as the case may likely be today, people should rely directly upon:

- ❖ Holiness - in its absolute vibrational form
- ❖ Ethics - a clearly superior MIMS based upon obvious facts of right and wrong.

Conclusions?

The author has no hard conclusions about morality as a simulation. Firstly the presumptions and assumptions are already (plainly) numerous. The variables are “out of control” and then there’s the clear lack of data. The main conclusion is that more study is needed (by the author and data scientists). The *assumptions* of moral authority prevalent in religious institutions like The Church are probably wrong. But so are the moral relativists, and we’re seeing the rampant destructive forces of this “battle of good and evil” in the streets today. But what does seem to be true is that Holiness as a wave or energy guide might be incredibly important to mankind, if for no other reason than the desire to justify harming one another. This should tell us something about ourselves.⁶⁹ It also seems like a good hypothesis that ethics is a superior MIMS to morality. Whatever function is being simulated for, morality has a tendency to slip into the anti-mimsical territory and destroy lives, and this may be something that needs to be studied *with gusto*⁷⁰ **now**, to prevent future destruction. It is also possible that morality is being weaponized by hidden figures for shadowy purposes. But it seems to be a fetching problem, and not necessarily a conspiracy. It is, however, an important discussion that needs to be had in pre-engineering the New Religion, or even just revitalizing Christendom⁷¹ (or other traditional religions being hit hard by social media instigated changes and the times⁷²).

⁶⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yErKTVdETpw>

⁶⁹ What that is, the jury is still “out”

⁷⁰ After data: probably AI learning machines to determine cost/benefit analyses

⁷¹ https://www.academia.edu/50934929/New_Christendom

⁷² Like Buddhism. Celestial Master Taoism might die out, for the first time in its history 3 men all claim lineage to the Celestial Grandmaster title. Meanwhile the CCP has threatened the very existence of Tibetan Buddhism as they kidnapped the Panchen Lama and the Dalai Lama has threatened to not reincarnate. Islam of course is a huge mess with ISIS/ISIL.

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